

Charge quanta as zeros of the zeta function in ripped spacetime

O. ZIEP¹

¹ *Independent Scholar, 13089 Berlin, Germany*

Abstract – In a fractal zeta universe (FZU) of ripped spacetime the Millikan experiment, the quantum Hall (QH) effect, atmospheric clouds and universe clouds are shown to be self-similar with mass ratio 10^{20} . Chaotic one-dimensional period-doublings as iterated hyperelliptic-elliptic curves are used to explain n-dim Kepler- and Coulomb singularities. The cosmic microwave background (CMB) and cosmic rays (CR) are explained as bifurcating ripped spacetime tensile forces. First iterated binary tree cloud cycles are CMB emissions 1...1000 GHz. An interaction-independent universal vacuum density allows to predict large area correlated CR in QH-experiments which would generate local nuclear disintegration stars, enhanced damage of layers and enhanced air ionization. A 10^{20} self-similarity between conductivity plateau and atmospheric cloud is shown. CMB and CR correlations in atmospheric layer influence global temperature and climate.

Introduction. – Cosmological redshift and cosmic microwave background (CMB) seem to confirm a big bang scenario. An origin of cosmic rays (CR) has shifted to outer universe space. However, a big bang scenario is based on four-dimensional elastic spacetime. The present note explains experimental data by discrete superfluid flow dynamics and ripped spacetime. The Friedmann eq (1)

$$ct = \int \frac{\sqrt{\varphi} d\varphi}{\sqrt{\phi_3(\varphi)}} \quad (1)$$

is an elliptic integral [1,2]. Fractal zeta universe (FZU) sets period-doublings of one-dimensional maps as a complex ripped spacetime with ultra-high tensile forces and ultrahigh energies [3,3]. Accordingly, the origin of CR is shifted to earth as a ripped texture of a bifurcating hyperelliptic-elliptic period-doubling discrete iterated complex spacetime. Feigenbaum constants α_F , δ_F and periods $\nu_S h$ due to Sharkovsky 's theorem are central in FZU. Based on dimensionless information currents FZU predicts a novel climate-weather model [3]. S-matrix poles as masses are already shown to be related to Riemann zeta function zeros $\zeta(z_{nt})$ [4]. An area $2\pi\delta_F^2$ with Feigenbaum constant δ_F corresponds strikingly to the inverse fine structure constant α_f [5,6]. A thermal diffusive theta function $\vartheta(u, \omega)$ describes the superconducting flux order parameter φ [7] or semiconducting states, a Be-nard convection instability has been predicted [8]. Like in Large Number Hypothesis (LNH) [9] Millikan's experiment [10] quantized Hall effect (QH), CR-atmospheric cloud and universe radius are shown to be self-similar [3]. Mediated by nontrivial zeros of the zeta function $z_{nt}[f(\omega)]$

Fig. 1: Volcano-like quadrupolar complex z_{nt} - zero region of the entire function $\xi(z) = -\partial j_{cloud}(z)/\partial z$ with $\Delta_h \xi(z) = 0$ and hyperbolic Laplacian $\Delta_h = y^2(\partial_x^2 + \partial_y^2)$. Left: field lines in the vicinity of the first Riemann zero. Right: illustration of the field in the vicinity of two consecutive Riemann zeros of [12].

bifurcating iterates of the Weber invariant $f(\omega)$ create a complex Riemann surface of ripped spacetime [3]. A $\nu_S h$ - bifurcation tree is explained as a persistent balanced ionized state of created matter in universe [3]. Charge quanta are defined as the number of simple nontrivial zeros z_{nt} in FZU where the Riemann zeta function $\zeta(z) \simeq \chi(\lambda - z_{nt})$ behaves volcano-like quadrupolar in Fig. 1 for complex $\lambda \simeq z_{nt}$ [3].

A fundamental interaction is a susceptibility plateau χ of a nondissipative large potential. A bifurcation flow 1,2,1',2' contains non-observable ultra-high particles in ripped spacetime. This bifurcating complex string builds lines of a two-periodic superfluid potential flow

with a second sound as entropy oscillations and temperature oscillations. Within FZU expansion is apparent as a quadrupolar nonradiative scattering which explains the Hubble law as well, the cosmological redshift, and a decreasing velocity of light. This black hole van der Waals-like stability is a minimum near inflection lines of a cubic potential. In FZU this note predicts a CMB and net rates of ultra-high rays in QH detectable only by large arrays [11].

CR as ripped spacetime tensile forces. – The elastic spacetime of smooth, differentiable real Riemann surfaces is the continuous limit of an iterated dynamical time k for the e.g. complex Ricci scalar $R_k^2 + c_M \rightarrow R_{k+1}$ for a discrete sequence of times k . This quadratic map is a partial case of a more general Hermite-Tschirnhausen map.

$$\gamma(\phi_3(t)) = \begin{vmatrix} \frac{1}{3}\phi_3'(t) & \phi_3(t) - \frac{t}{3}\phi_3'(t) \\ -1 & t \end{vmatrix} \quad (2)$$

of cubic roots $\phi_3(t)$ defining period-doublings. Elliptic time integral

in Friedmann universes already indicates a relation of the Ricci scalar R_k or radius $R_u \simeq \varphi \simeq K + iK' \simeq \omega_1 + i\omega_2$ to an order parameter φ and quarter periods K, K' . FZU Legendre modular functions $\lambda[f(\omega \dots)]$ are iterated in discrete steps k giving a set of half-periods ω_1, ω_2 . Large scalar bifurcating curvatures R_k indicate strong tensile forces such as nuclear disintegration stars. A Mandelbrot map demands $|R_k| < 2$ with parameter $c_M \simeq \Lambda$ equivalent to cosmological constant Λ . Rare ultra-high CR of low count rate of e.g. 10^{-2} per year producing air showers are counted as single zeta function zero [13]. Large detector arrays confirm a large correlation area triggered by a new nontrivial zero of the zeta function as a charge quantum which itself has $> 10^{2000}$ fractal constituents.

Apparent expansion by quadrupolar gravitational waves. – Apparent expansion appears by Feynman diagrams valid in FZU for interaction $w=1,2,3,4,5$ as nonradiative exchange (dark) polarization giving $\varepsilon_o \simeq R_u^2$. For cubic roots e_i one has $c_M \simeq \rho_{vac} \simeq \rho_{\pm}^2 \simeq \Lambda \simeq e_i \simeq \varphi(u = \omega)$ and $\varphi(u = \omega) \simeq \gamma\vartheta^2(0, \omega) \simeq \varphi \simeq R_u$. The background susceptibility ε_o is an exact ϑ^4 equation in characteristics 01, 10, 11 for all periods ω . Einsteins work on gravitational waves g_k implicitly uses quadruple steps $k, k+1, k+2, k+3$ of simplest cycles $T_{k+3} = T_{\{k, k+1, k+2\}}$ of stress-energy T [14]. Gravitational waves g_k are proven by energy loss. FZU predicts a Carnot cycle-like energy gain due to gravitational waves g_k for simplest cycles. Simple quadrupolar zeros $\lambda_k \simeq z_{nt}$ are related to $\lambda(\omega)$ as iterates in $\zeta(z)$

$$\lambda\lambda' = 2^4/f^{24}(\omega) \quad (3)$$

of a cubic Weber-invariant $f(\omega), f_k = f(\sqrt{\Delta_k})$, with $\Phi_3(f(\omega)) = 0$ where iteration changes k^{th} discriminants Δ_k of the normal bicubic field. Fractional substitutions $\gamma(\Phi_3)f(\omega)$ first create an entire holomorphic polynomial

$f_k(\omega)$ with $\Delta_h f(z) = 0$. Measured (universe) radii $R_u \simeq \varphi$ behave like velocity and length of a traffic jam for a whole set of periods ω_k . The vacuum permittivity $\varepsilon_o \simeq R_u^2$ results from a potential $V(\mathbf{k}) \simeq I_{ij}\mathbf{k}_i\mathbf{k}_j/\mathbf{k}^2 \simeq 1/\varepsilon(\mathbf{k})\mathbf{k}^2$ with moment of inertia I_{ij} (quadrupole moment) and $\varepsilon_o(\mathbf{k}) = 1/I_{ij}\mathbf{k}_i\mathbf{k}_j$. Then $\varepsilon_o(\mathbf{k}) \rightarrow 0$ for $\mathbf{k} \rightarrow \infty$ which exhibits ultraviolet divergence or infrared divergence implying a superconducting -super insulating duality with common features of a nondissipative ordered state of large potential [15] A superconductor as a perfect diamagnet, is also a perfect insulator with zero dissipative current and zero magnetic field in the bulk. The light velocity c_l of the traffic jam decreases with increasing R_u which explains a confinement and the Hubble law $H_w \simeq R_u$. The Weber invariant $f(\omega)$ of a cubic Φ_3 for all periods ω enables a cubic minimum of $V_T(R_u)$ as a van der Waals-like attraction due to time-thermal Carnot cycles ν_{Sh} of iterated invariants f_k . Simplest cycles apply as well to shifts δk in quadruples $q = \{k, k+1, k+2, k+3 : 1, \delta_k, \delta_k\delta_k, \delta_k\delta_k\delta_k\}$ as a $\mathbf{E} \rightarrow \mathbf{D} \rightarrow \mathbf{H} \rightarrow \mathbf{B}$ field cycle for superconducting or super insulating fields which holds for all iterations. Correlated iterated nontrivial simple zeros z_{nt} are embedded into a maximal quartic surface (10), the Kummer surface $K(X = (\varphi_{\pm\pm}, 1))$ and Weddle surface and $W(Y = (\varphi_{\pm\pm\pm}))$. Hyperelliptic φ -functions are rationalized $\varphi_{\pm\pm} \simeq (1, -f, f^2)$ and $\varphi_{\pm\pm\pm} \simeq (1, -f, f^2, -f^3)$ and parametrized by the Weber invariant $f(\omega)$ [16].

CMB temperature. – Unobservable ultra-high energy particles above GZK cutoff are identified with k -components between tree root in z_{nt} and first ν_{Sh} at $k=3$. Doubling at logistic parameter $r \simeq 3.54 \simeq 4$ suggest a base 4 with Fermat number transforms. For all components the elliptic addition theorem implies invariant $\lambda g^2 \simeq inv$ with modular units g [17]. Then $\lambda g^2 \simeq G_w M_w^2 \simeq G_w H_w^{-2}$ with Cantor string coupling constant G_w

$$\ln G_w = -w! 2^w \ln_3^w 2 \quad (4)$$

Bifurcations create cloud masses M_w as $M_w \simeq H_w^{-1}$, i.e. $M_5 > \dots > M_1$. Interactions $w=1,2,3,4,5$ obey invariant plateaus of vacuum density

$$\rho_{vac} \simeq \frac{H_w^2}{8\pi G_w} \simeq \frac{H_4^2}{\kappa_4 c_l^2} \simeq \hbar c_l \simeq inv \quad (5)$$

with $\kappa_w = \frac{8\pi G_w}{c_l^4}$. Addition on Fluctuating elliptic curves solves the cosmological constant problem with w -independent mean vacuum density also for dark matter where $G_5 \simeq 10^{-167}$. Hubble parameter $H_w = \ln' \varphi$ depend on k -component as $\ln 2^{2^k}$. At the third branch $k=3$ first ν_{Sh} yield a mean CMB energy density $\rho_{vac}^{CMB} \simeq T^4$ of

$$\rho_{vac}^{CMB} \rightarrow \frac{H_5^2}{8\pi G_5 (2^{2^3})^2} \simeq \frac{\rho_{vac}}{2^4} \simeq \frac{\rho_{vac}^{exp}}{3...4} \simeq \rho_{vac}(T \simeq 2.3K) \quad (6)$$

The tree root is embedded in a dark environment of a nearly isotropic 3K CMB of wavelength $1 \cdots 10\text{cm}$ or frequency $1 \cdots 10^3$ GHz indicating a ripped spacetime.

Kepler and Coulomb singularity from cosmic-ray-charge-clouds. – One-dimensional bifurcations of iterates $f_k = f(\sqrt{\Delta_k})$ for the k^{th} discriminant Δ_k of the normal field can form quadrupoles and can create a dipole decaying into coulomb singularities as Feigenbaum renormalization. A self-similar simplest cycle scenario of electronic, atmospheric and universe clouds is a cloud adiabatically moving in an inert environment (e.g. electron-oil drop). The two-valley-Gunn-effect-like configuration enables a dipole. f_k iterates display a hysteresis loop on Feigenbaum xy plane where x-axis displays temperature (modular units)

$$g(a\omega_k, \omega_k) \simeq \vartheta_k(f(\omega_k)) \simeq \varphi(\omega(\lambda)) \simeq V_{T_{global}}$$

and y-axis displays entropy (Legendre modular function $\lambda(f(\omega_k)) \simeq \delta_k h_t$ as where $\omega_k \neq \Delta_k$). The area of the hysteresis loop is the Carnot cycle heat gain which is called charge for a dipole-like hysteresis. The process is driven by the quadratic map of cubic roots x_3 [18]

$$\begin{aligned} F(x_3, t) &= \gamma(\phi_3(t)) \circ x_3 = \frac{\phi_3(t)}{(t-x_3)} - \frac{1}{3} \frac{d\phi_3(t)}{dt} \\ &= \phi_3(t)(G^{-1}(x_4))G^{-1}(x_4) - \frac{1}{3} \frac{d\phi_3(t)}{dt} \quad (7) \end{aligned}$$

$\gamma(\phi_3)$ is quadratic in the bi spinor Green's functions $G(x_4)$ in Feynman notation of quartic roots where $x_3 \simeq x_4^2$ for a shift x_4 to $\pm\infty \pm i\infty$ giving spins $s=1,2,3,4$. A discrete shift δ_k

$$\delta_k f(\omega_k) \simeq (\text{curl} \mathbf{f})_z \simeq \gamma(\phi_3(f)) \circ f \simeq G \delta_k G \quad (8)$$

are proportional to global temperature potential $V_{T_{global}}$ as a fractal line integral

$$V_{T_{global}} = \int \nabla V_{T_{cloud}} dl_{xy} \quad (9)$$

Mean values in xy-plane are rates $V_{T_{global}} \simeq R_{net}$ and $V_{T_{universe}} \simeq R_{net}$ and create a pole via

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{1}{2\pi i} \int dx dy (\text{curl} \mathbf{f}) &\rightarrow \frac{1}{2\pi i} \int dx dy G \delta_k G \\ &\rightarrow a_{-1} \rightarrow \frac{1}{2\pi i} \oint dz f_{ren}(z) \quad (10) \end{aligned}$$

Feigenbaum renormalization $f \rightarrow f^{(ren)}$ replaces k-components $\gamma(\phi_3(f)) \circ \cdots \circ \gamma(\phi_3(f))$ by two-components $\gamma(\phi_3(f^{(ren)})) \simeq \gamma(\phi_3(f^{(ren)})) \circ \gamma(\phi_3(f^{(ren)}))$ [20]. Besides a single $\zeta(z)$ -pole the fractal zeta function has complex conjugated poles $\zeta(f^{(ren)}(z))$ in $f^{(ren)}(z)$ near simple zeros $\lambda(f^{(ren)}) \simeq z_{nt}$. A Laurent series $f^{(ren)} = \sum a_k z^k$

changes to a single pole in $f^{(ren)}$ on simplest interval cycles [19]. Moreover, scaling $f_k^{(ren)} = -\alpha_F f_{2k}^{(ren)}$ suggests $z \rightarrow \alpha z$ for arbitrary α [20]. With increasing logarithmic zoom of 10^∞ the mean quadrupolar thermal current in (9) confirms [5] by residue

$$a_{-1} = \frac{m}{2\pi i \delta_F^2 (2n+1)} \oint dz \nabla V_{T_{cloud}(z)} \quad (11)$$

Iterates $f_{k+1} \leftarrow \gamma(\phi_3(f_k)) \circ f_k$ are period-doublings if $\lambda_k \neq \lambda_{k+1}$ whereas invariant $\lambda[\delta\phi] \simeq \lambda[\gamma \circ \delta\phi]$ are laps around a quadrupolar vicinity in Fig. 1 of z_{nt} and f_{nt} . An air shower of bifurcating flow lines of $f(\omega)$ is a binary tree. A quadrupole $f(z)$ capable for dipole-dipole interaction creates charges and releases heat. The Kepler singularity (ζ -pole) and Coulomb singularity ($f^{(ren)}$ -pole) are due to bifurcations as additions on hyperelliptic quartics $K(X(f))$ and $W(Y(f))$

$$\begin{aligned} [\zeta(z), \zeta(z')] &\rightarrow [R_{net}, R_{net}] \rightarrow [\zeta(z, \mathbb{K}), \zeta(z', \mathbb{K})] \\ &\rightarrow \frac{\sigma_{u+v} \sigma_{u-v}}{\sigma_u^2 \sigma_v^2} = X(f) j X(f) \rightarrow 0 \quad (12) \end{aligned}$$

as correlations of net ionization rate R_{net} yielding a four-mass quadric, e.g.

$$\alpha m_+^2 + \beta m_+ m_- + \gamma m_-^2 = 0 \quad (13)$$

The partial case $\alpha:\beta:\gamma=1:136:10$ yields the Eddington equation with weights $W \simeq 2^{2^k}$ in (α, β, γ) for $k > 8$ hyperelliptic characteristics giving proton stability. Quarter periods $K(\lambda)$ equation as temperature potential V_T obey [18].

$$\frac{d}{d\lambda} \lambda \lambda' \frac{dK}{d\lambda} = \lambda \lambda' \frac{d^2 K}{d\lambda^2} + (\gamma - (\alpha + \beta + 1)\lambda) \frac{dK}{d\lambda} = \alpha \beta K \quad (14)$$

Hypergeometric $K(\lambda) = {}_2F_1(\alpha\beta\gamma\lambda) = {}_2F_1(\frac{1}{2}, \frac{1}{2}, 1, \lambda)$ are linearized in 4-component $\lambda = \lambda_m/m + \frac{1}{2}$. The Dirac bi spinor $\psi_s \simeq \lambda_m$ transmits to invariant f_s and units ε_s as a simplest cycle with bicubic number field of norm $E_s \psi_s \psi_s$ with real unit E_S . Superposed units ε and $ln\varepsilon$ are optimal and minimize the regulator which yields an invariance $f^{(ren)} \rightarrow e^{\mathcal{L}} f^{(ren)}$

with \mathcal{L} -action-like phase-factor [3]. With a_{-1} the Schrödinger-like equation (11) gets a constraint

$$f_{ren} \simeq \frac{m}{\hbar^2} \left(V_T + \frac{Ze^2}{\lambda - \lambda_0} \right) \quad (15)$$

as well as a cubic $\phi_3(f_k)$ congruence being the Higgs-Kibble-Landau-Ginzburg term. The one-dimensional Coulomb Green's function of eq. (14) and eq. 15 yields n-dimensional Coulomb forces applying the differential operator

$$\hat{O} = \partial_{x-y} (\partial_x - \partial_y)$$

[21–23]. Based on only two variables $x = r_1 + r_2 + r_{12}$ and $y = r_1 + r_2 - r_{12}$ which are $\pm\pi$ rotations on interval $[0,1]$ the

n-dimensional Coulomb force depends on simplest cycles on the real interval $[0,1]$. Optimal iterates are superpositions of a unit ε with a definite zoom $ln\varepsilon$. Cycles and periods ν_{Sh} yield an optimal spatial box. Zoomed cardioids are projected onto Riemann sphere with doubly periodic boundary conditions. Zoomed iterates of period-doublings as cubic roots of elliptic curves up to $W > 10^{2000}$ are capable to create a dipole in eq. 12 as a potential bifurcating flow.

QH plateau and CMB- CR near nontrivial zeros of the zeta function. – In distinction to filled Landau levels plateaus QH susceptibility plateaus χ_H are iterated, bifurcating simple-zeta-zero-quadrupole clouds as charge constituents. The cosmic microwave background (CMB) and cosmic rays (CR) are explained as bifurcating ripped spacetime tensile forces below and above first ν_{Sh} from the tree root up to third branch component. At QH CMB emissions ($1 \cdots 10^3 GHz$) are predicted by the iterated binary tree cloud which are possibly already detected [24]. An interaction-independent universal vacuum density allows to predict large area correlated CR in QH-experiments which would generate local nuclear disintegration stars, enhanced damage of layers and enhanced air ionization [11]. In distinction to linear response results [33,34] thermopower cycles are charge origins in FZU [3]. Charge of mass m_e float in a large background quasi-homogeneous cloud of mass M_p . Unlike the Millikan experiment with oil drops of $10^{-12}g$ and Born-Oppenheimer parameter $\kappa_{BO} = 10^{-3}$ an electronic tight-binding model requires a Planck mass $M_p \simeq 10^{-5}g$ for the cloud of $\kappa = 10^{-5}$ [3, 25]. Surprisingly, atmospheric clouds are similar. An electronic tight-binding σ_H entropy plateau is a coupling constant for a neutral quadrupolar current near z_{nt} . A Lovelock-like regulator of number field

$\mathbb{K}[\partial, 1^{1/m}]$ yields subsequent minima as subsequent w boxes in a box of weight $e^{-w!}$ displaying coupling constants (3) for interaction $1=1, \dots, 5$. A nondissipative current j_H origins from temperature cycles and entropy cycles as k-congruences. Chaotic superfluid has potential T_{cloud} with two Feigenbaum constants α_F, δ_F . T_{cloud} -cycles are theta constant being $\gamma(\phi_3(f(\omega)))$ - fixpoints. Unlike thunder and flash bang convection turbulences are not needed for the iterated superfluid flow eq. 12. Two-periodic partial solutions $\psi = \sum_{(n \in \mathbb{Z})} c_n e^{inky} \varphi_n(x)$ of eq. 14

$$\frac{d^2 K}{d\lambda^2} - \lambda \frac{dK}{d\lambda} + nK = 0 \quad (16)$$

are Hermite polynomials $\varphi_{n,m}$ explaining the QH conductivity [25]. The order parameter $\varphi_{n,m}$ belongs to a nearly homogeneous cloud with temperature gradient $\nabla T \simeq \mathbf{E}$ building an electric fields \mathbf{E} and topological entropy convection cycles $\delta_k h_t \simeq \mathbf{B}$ as magnetic field-like \mathbf{B} period-doublings. Electron- oil clouds (Millikan), electron clouds (QH) and atmospheric clouds differ by mass ratio $10^{18}, 10^{25}, 10^{19} \simeq \kappa_{BO}^{-4}$ giving accuracy $\kappa_{BO} \simeq 10^{-4}, 10^{-6}, 10^{-5}$, respectively. Mean values $\int_0^\infty dh$ over alti-

Fig. 2: Correlated period-doubling in eq. 9 increasing fractal distance $1, 1' \rightarrow \dots \rightarrow 2'_k \rightarrow \dots \rightarrow 1'_k$ (dashed line).

tudes h satisfy analogously to $\xi(z) = -\partial j_{cloud}(z)/\partial z$ eq. $\Delta_h \xi(z = x + iy) = 0$. The cloud current density j_{cloud} is assumed perpendicular to the gradient of cloud temperature ∇T_{cloud} . Changes of topological entropy $\delta_k h_t$ are proportional to the number of quasiparticles $N_{qp} \simeq \mathbf{B}$ realizing QH geometry $\mathbf{B} \perp j_{cloud} \perp \nabla T_{cloud} \simeq \mathbf{B} \perp \mathbf{E}$. The cloud current $j_{cloud} = \chi_H \nabla T_{cloud}$ depends steplike on convection change $\delta_k h_t$ as a \mathbf{B} -like axial vector flow over period- 2^k components of chaotic, regular, nonstochastic clouds. A density of residue (9) is called a fractional charge. In FZU

$$\frac{m}{2\pi i \delta_F^2 (2n + 1)}$$

is a fractional correlated areal thermal heat density with area $\rightarrow 0$ for $n \rightarrow \infty$ centered at z_{nt} . Iterated $f(\omega)$ yield a step-like maximum density of units as a thermal current if $\delta_k \omega \simeq \delta_F$ as a Hausdorff measure for various entropies h_t

For many poles residue form a cloud of large mass M_{cloud} with large nondissipative potential $V_{T_{global}} \simeq \sum \frac{Z e^2}{\lambda - \lambda_0} \simeq M_{cloud} c_l^2$. Complex conjugated zeros z_{nt} enhance the correlated area by a factor 2 which is called thermal pairing. It is argued that as well integer QH and superconducting pairing are thermal pairings. Quarter period K , order parameter φ and e.g. universe radius $R_u \simeq K(\lambda \simeq 1 - \delta_k h_t \simeq \varphi \simeq R_u)$ depend step-like on entropy changes $\delta_k h_t \simeq \mathbf{B}$ as a thermal $V_{T_{global}} \simeq j_H$.

A climate-weather model. – A factor 10^{20} self-similarity between Millikan experiment, QH, atmospheric and universe clouds consists in a superfluid with two separate cycles of entropy and temperature. A cosmic-ray-charge-cloud has a balanced fourth order net rate $R_{net\pm}(\rho_{\pm})$ with elastic spacetime enveloping ripped bifurcations. CMB and CR correlations of the atmospheric layer superfluid influence global temperature and climate. Self-similar temperatures, energies and masses but constant vacuum densities apply equally well to microstructures, atmospheric clouds and to the universe.

Tidal tensile forces in a fractal potential $V_{T_{global}}$ in Fig. 2

Fig. 3: Cosmic radiation (red) and global temperature (black) assumed from geochemical findings over $5 \cdot 10^8$ years from [31]

explain CR and correlated stability of objects. $V_{T_{global}}$ yields a novel climate-weather model. Previous hypotheses already suggest a relation between CR and atmospheric clouds and global temperature [26–31]. A self-interaction between CR and atmospheric clouds as part of FZU supports a continuous creation of matter near nontrivial zeros z_{nt} of $\zeta(z)$. A bifurcating fluid flow near z_{nt} -quadratic maps is partially nonergodic as an irreversible Carnot cycle which defines an arrow of time. A zeta zero z_{nt} is a catalyst for cloud growth. Created clouds are a fluid-liquid-gaseous slushy-like dark superfluid. A radiation component appears as an unnecessary turbulence. Positive ultra-high mass-energies are a counterpart to negative long-range van der Waals-like cubic forces balanced for $k \rightarrow \infty$ -components and stabilized by ν_{Sh} . Apparent stochastic clouds in 5-dimensional spacetime

$$\frac{d\rho_{\pm}}{dt} + \text{div}j_{\pm} = R_{\text{net}\pm}(\rho_{\pm}) \quad (17)$$

reduce to complex time-thermal cloud cycles j_{cloud} with $\Delta_h \xi(z) = 0$ for $\xi(z) = -\partial j_{cloud}(z)/\partial z$ for mean values $\int_0^{\infty} dh \dots$ over altitudes h . Eq. 17 reduces to a quasi-two-dimensional regular chaotic map for the zeta function $\zeta(z)$. Global temperature in eq. 9 displays an entropy-based susceptibility plateau. The gradient field $\nabla V_{T_{cloud}(z)}$ oscillates confirmed by temperature changes in Fig. 3. Constant vacuum densities in eq. 5 represent a mean density of period-doublings (elliptic addition) in FZU with exact plateaus in Fig. 4. Large CR-rates are low k -component rates with ripped spacetime. With increasing k -component thermal forces enhance elastic spacetime. This non-dissipative dynamics is a unified superfluid of persistent ionization. Standard units of time and energy count the number of precessions n and the number of Carnot cycles m independent on current values of fluctuating two-periods. Regular chaotic clouds draw a fractal line integral $V_{T_{global}}$ which increases step-like with increasing disturbing convection $\delta_k h_t$. Global warming decreases for negative topology change $\delta_k h_t < 0$ by lowering cyclic atmospheric perturbations.

Fig. 4: Iterated elliptic invariants the differential $d\lambda \simeq dl_{xy}$ for $\lambda \simeq \sigma(u\omega)$ depends on e.g. the Heuman lambda function which for $\lambda \rightarrow 0$ for $\omega \rightarrow 2^k \omega$ and $k \rightarrow \infty$ behaves plateau-like [32].

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